

Distribution Pattern of Markets Places in Kachin State; The Case of Myitkyina

Soe Soe Khin*

Abstract

Myitkyina is the capital of Kachin State, on the northern part of Myanmar, and it is located on the western bank of the Ayeyarwady River. The bank's plain is Kachin State, which shares borders with China. The average elevation of the study area is 476 feet above sea level. At the present time, the area of Myitkyina is 104.82 sq.-kilometers. Mode of transportation, which connect Myitkyina to other towns of Myanmar, consists of roadways, railways and airways. The total population of Myitkyina was 2,341,087. Market places form an important urban land use pattern, and hence, this paper revolves around a case study of market distribution in Myitkyina. The study area consists of 3 permanent markets and 16 morning markets. In the case study, markets distribution and structure were analyzed by: (1) distribution patterns of markets places, (2) differences in size and function of markets, and (3) major controlling factors of marketplace in Myitkyina. Finally, analysis indicates that distribution of marketplaces and their functions depend on location, population and other factors.

Key words: *Markets, location, Transportation, items, factors*

Introduction

A marketplace refers to an activity of buying or selling a product. A marketplace is a small area in a town or a city, where goods are bought or sold, often outdoors. Marketplaces are usually jammed with buyers and sellers. Some markets are large and sell a wide range of goods, while others could be small and limited to particular products. Some markets are located at easily accessible areas, while others are not. This indicates the importance of accessibility and availability in market functioning. Although some markets depend on nearby customers, others attract wide range of customers from both nearby and further distances. Myitkyina is an urbanized capital city of Kachin State. It is one of the most important administrative, commercial, cultural, and populous areas with higher infrastructural development. It is located between north latitude 25° 22' and 25° 25', and east longitude 97° 19' and 97° 23'. respectively on the west bank of the Ayeyarwady River, just less than 40 kilometers (25 miles) from the confluence of its two head streams (The Malikha and Maikha River). Myitkyina has the northern most river port and railway station in Myanmar. It comprises 28 wards, which are bounded on the north by Palana village, demarcated on the east and south by Ayeyarwady river and in the west by Nankway creek. The average elevation of the study area is 467 (feet) above sea level. It covers an area of 41.46 (sq.-miles) and had a population of 234108 in 2019. The population density of the town is 5785 per square mile. The population distribution is uneven in the study area. The most densely populated area is near the town center and the marketplace due to its superior quality of transportation to carry out economic activities in comparison to other wards. The study area receives (cwa type of climate) humid subtropical climate. The Ayeyarwady river is the main drainage of the study area. It represents not only the major freshwater resources of the study area, but also the lifeblood of the entire country. Most of the study area is covered with alluvium soil. Myitkyina is in Kachin state, northern part of Myanmar, and the state itself is rich with forest and natural resources, so it grows many fruits, flowers, plants and vegetables due to rain and fertility. The agricultural works in Wine Maw township is expansive. Paddy fields and gardening works are mainly made in Wine Maw township. It is the main supply of various vegetables for the markets in Myitkyina. The state exports its products to middle and lower parts of Myanmar and neighbouring countries. It also imports necessary goods from middle and lower parts of

* Dr, Associate Professor, Department of Geography, Bago University

Myanmar. Myitkyina has good transportation to other parts of Myanmar in terms of railway, motorway and airway. As a result, it has a good trade system.

In this paper, in relation to the distribution pattern of markets places in Myitkyina, permanent markets (Myoma Zay gyi 1, Myoma Zay gyi 2 and Ye Sin Kwin Zay) and morning markets (located in the wards/ small markets) will be considered. However, other street vendor-oriented markets will not be considered. The following questions will be answered in this research paper: (1) what are the distribution patterns of markets places? (2) why are there different market sizes and functions? (3) what are the major controlling factors of marketplaces? It is considered that the distributed goods and market location do not describe the consumer's behavior. The locational factors, controlling the distribution of markets, are necessary to know from geographic point of view.

Research questions

- what are the distribution patterns of markets places?
- why are there different market sizes and functions?
- what are the major controlling factors of marketplaces?

Study area

Myitkyina is located in northern Myanmar and western side of Ayeyawady river. Area of Myitkyina is 104.8 square-kilometers (40.46 square miles). It is located between north latitude 25° 22' and 25° 25' and east longitude 97° 19' and 97° 23'. It is elevated about 476 feet above sea level. As a drainage system, the Ayeyarwady River is flowing through eastern parts of Myitkyina with north south direction at its southern part. On the west of Myitkyina, Nangwae creek is flowing through the western part with north south direction.

Figure (1) Location map of Myitkyina

Material and Methods

Primary data and secondary data are used to present geographical analysis of marketplaces in Myitkyina. To see the distribution patterns of the “Markets” location, field observations were made. To know the spatial and functional changes, open talks and interviews with some consumers, authorities and shops owners and were conducted. Field observations provide a clear overview of market functions in the study area.

Result

Types of market and shops

A market is an area in which the conditions of competition applied to the product concerned are the same for all traders. The same factors used in delineating relevant-product markets should be used to define the relevant markets. 19 markets exist in Myitkyina. There are two types of markets in the study area of Myitkyina. The study area has 3 permanent markets (Zay gyi) and 16 morning markets (zay lay) which are owned by Township Development Affairs Department.

Permanent Markets (Zay gyi)

The permanent markets are Myoma Zay (1), Myoma Zay (2) and Ye Sin Kwin Zays. Myoma Zay (1) and Myoma Zay (2) are reinforced concrete buildings, located in Myoma ward. Ye Sin Kwin market is a brick-nog building, located in the Min Yard ward. These types of market sell various kinds of things in the permanent market on permanent shops.

Permanent markets were established previously, but Ye Sin Kwin market was established after 1994. It is based on the increasing population along with good transportation networks in Myitkyina. The permanent markets are in the southeastern part of the Myitkyina and on the west bank of Ayeyarwady river. Myoma Zay (1) has 940 shops. 720 shops are found in Myoma Zay (2) and Ye Sin Kwin market owns 178 shops.

Figure (2) Variation in total number of shops in permanent market in Myitkyina

Source: Market department

Total number of shops varies among the permanent markets in Myitkyina. Myoma market 1 (Myoma Zay1) has the largest number of shops and Ye sin kwin market (Ye Sin kwin Zay) has the smallest number of shops. Myoma market 1 (Myoma Zay 1) has 940 shops while Ye sin kwin market (Ye Sin kwin Zay) has 178 shops. Myoma market 2 (Myoma Zay 2) has a relatively large number of shops with 720 shops respectively (See Figure 3).

Markets have different levels and sell different items. For the analysis, items sold in the markets of Myoma market 1 (Myoma Zay 1) and Myoma market 2 (Myoma Zay 2) of Myitkyina, are clothes, pots, gold, jewelry, medicines, electronics, grocery, dry goods, vegetables and meats. On the other hand, main selling items of Ye sin kwin market (Ye Sin kwin Zay) are meat, fish, dry goods and vegetables. Myoma market 1 has the largest market area (162348 Sq.-feet) and Ye sin kwin market has the lowest market area 47655 (sq.-feet) within permanent markets.

Figure (3) Variation in total number of shops in permanent market in Myitkyina

Source: Market department

Morning markets (Zay Lay)

Morning markets open daily from early in the morning. There is a wide range of stalls in the food paths, selling newly harvested vegetables, fresh meat, fish, clothing and dry goods. Myitkyina has 16 morning markets (Zay lay). Daily-use foodstuffs are mainly sold in the morning markets. Among the 28 wards in Myitkyina, the morning markets are only found in 16 wards. The morning markets are mostly found in wide area wards, near permanent markets. Total number of shops varies among the morning markets (Zay lay) in Myitkyina. Yangyiaung ward morning market has the largest number of shops and Myothitgyi ward morning market has the smallest number of shops. Yangyiaung ward morning market has 102 shops, while Myothitgyi morning market has 43 shops (See Figure 4). Types of shops varies in each market, depending on the customer’s requirement in their respective ward.

Figure (4) Distribution pattern of morning markets (Zay Lay) and total number of shops

Source: Market Department

Discussion

Permanent Markets

Myitkyina, the capital city of Kachin State, is populous. Most of the residents are Kachin, Myanmar and Shan nationals. There are civil offices, military regiments, training schools and universities in Myitkyina. Thus, it has more consumers. Regional products are sold as whole sales and retails in the markets. The shop keepers in the markets import necessary daily-use goods, pots, plates, grocery items, electrical goods and construction materials from lower parts of Myanmar and neighboring China. There are many jewellery shops in the markets because Kachin State is rich with minerals such as jade and gold. Kachin traditional clothes, China-made warm cloths and blankets are mainly sold in the permanent markets (Myoma Zay Gyi1 & 2).

Figure (5) Distribution pattern of markets in Myitkyina

Source: UTM map

Figure (6) Distribution pattern of markets places in Myitkyina

Source: Field survey

Morning Market (Zay Lay)

The busiest period in morning markets is 5 am to 9 am, daily. Meat, fish, vegetables, fruits, grocery items and seasonal products are mainly sold in the markets, in addition to traditional food of Kachin and Shan nationals. While there are a lot of freshwater fish in Myitkyina, beside Ayeyarwady river, Wine Maw township, on the eastern bank of Ayeyarwady river, mainly supplier vegetable, flowers and fruits to the consumers of Myitkyina. In fact, Myitkyina and Wine Maw township are connected to each other by Bala Min Htin Bridge. There are 6 ethnic groups in Kachin state. Each ethnic group specializes in a specific traditional vocation. For example, Le Su ethnic group skillfully cultivate pineapples, breed pigs and produce honey straight from nest. Thus, the ward markets are full of local Kachin products. Most consumers living in the wards buy their necessary foodstuff in the nearby morning markets. Meat, fish, grocery, dry goods, vegetables and other daily products are mainly sold in the morning markets. In these markets, most of the sellers farms their own plants, whereas other demanded products of grocery and dry goods were bought from wholesale centers. In addition, farm raised chicken and pond bred fish are imported from Sagaing Region (Kanbalu and Shweboo townships) to the markets. As Kachin State is sharing borders with China, Chinese products, such as fruits, pots, plates and clothes are also sold in Myitkyina's morning markets.

Figure (7) Controlling factors of markets in Myitkyina

Source: Administrative Office

Distribution pattern of marketplaces are found in 3 zones. Calculation of market zone is based upon the number of markets existing in respective wards. Zone 1 consists of 13 wards. Zone 2 has 6 wards and zone 3 has 9 wards respectively. Furthermore, zone 1 has 10 markets and zone 2 has 9 markets. Zone 3 is located closer to downtown marketplaces, but further away from new wards (See Figure 5). In the study of marketplaces in Myitkyina, five major controlling factors are found. These factors are government policy, population, land use types, location, climate, distance to the river, accessibility and trade. In upgrade and revitalization of permanent markets, a new permanent market mainly depends on government policy. Some wide wards are far from the town center and marketplaces. Consequently, government authorities open morning markets in their respective wards. In market functioning, population is the most important factor. If population is gradually increased, the demand will also increase. If residential land use and ward area are narrow, marketplaces will not be found.

Myanmar's economy mainly depends on agriculture. Natural vegetation and resources depend on climate types and location. Myitkyina is located in the northern part of Myanmar. Therefore, forest products and natural resources are rich. Before 1994, distribution pattern of markets is found along the Ayeyarwady river in north-south direction. After 1994, distribution pattern of markets spread to other places, especially towards the east. Hence, markets distribution pattern of Myitkyina mainly depends on Ayeyarwady river. Since the past times, Myitkyina has been a trading center between China and Myanmar. Most of its economic works are based on natural resources. Regarding the transportation sector, Mandalay-Myitkyina railway is the most important support for regional trade and other social-works. In recent years, safe and sound highway connection such as Myitkyina_Laiza, Myitkyina_Bhamo and Myitkyina_Mandalay have being developed. Thus, accessibility and trade conditions are also important factors (See Figure 7).

Conclusion

Myitkyina is the capital of Kachin State, in northern part of Myanmar and located at the plain western bank of the Ayeyarwady River. It has 104.8 square-kilometers (40.46 square miles). Myitkyina is composed of (28) wards. In a case study of market area distribution in Myitkyina, two parts are divided as follows: (1) permanent markets (large markets) and (2) morning markets (small markets). The case study includes 19 markets, which consists of 3 permanent markets and 16 morning markets. Permanent markets open daily during day times, except Sabbath day. Some small markets are morning markets and the others are found in the evening. Some people from other parts of Myanmar move to Myitkyina to pursue their vocations such as stone finishing or weaving Kachin traditional cloths. As a result, there is a gradual increase in Myitkyina's population, which is expanding wards and creating new markets. Now Myitkyina has 19 markets. The large markets or permanent markets (Myoma Zay1, Myoma Zay 2 and Ye Sin Kwin Zay) distribute their goods to neighbouring townships and villages such as Putao, Wine Maw, She Pwe, San Htone, Sin Bo and Kan Pie Tea. These markets import their necessary goods from Shwe Bo, Mandalay and Yangon. They also import cloths and other daily-use goods from China. In return, Myitkyina exports jewellerys, gold, Kachin traditional cloths and agriculture products (e.g traditional medicines, fruits, tissue bananas) to other parts of Myanmar and China. To perform marketing functions, cars, motor cycles, bicycle, and 3-wheeled cycles are used in Myitkyina. Exports and imports are carried out by cars and trains. There are three zones in the studied marketplaces. 10 markets are included in zone one. 9 markets are included in zone two. Zone one is a place of whole and retail sales. It distributes vegetables, fruits and flower to other places in the morning. Zone two is a place of gardeners who sell their products to other places. They supply their products to the markets in zone one in the mornings. Permanent markets and morning markets do not exist in zone three since it is located closer to downtown area marketplaces. In urban areas, marketplaces are dispersed in downtown area, nearby downtown and suburban area. The number of markets in downtown area is 55 percent, that of nearby downtown area is 30 percent and suburban area is 15 percent respectively of all markets in Myitkyina (See Figure 6). Downtown area has 3 permanent large markets and wholesale centers. Depending on the permanent large markets, other economic activities and services are developed (e.g fashion shops, clinics, banks etc-). In the Neighbouring downtown area, 30 percent of morning markets (small markets) exist. In those areas, most of the retail sales are found. Most of the traders, buy their necessary goods from permanent markets and gardeners. Then they distribute the goods to consumers. Majority of consumers are the residents of marketplace wards. In suburban areas, retail market functions and primary products are found, where paddy fields and gardens exist. The market distribution pattern is found in mainly residential areas as a cluster pattern. The

three permanent markets (Myo Ma Zay 1, Myo Ma Zay 2 and Ye Sin Kwin Zay) exist in Myoma ward and Min Yard ward. These two wards are business areas of Myitkyina. The morning markets are dispersed in Myitkyina. They are spreading along the Ayeyarwady river, because they are mainly based on the primary products (e.g fresh fish, meat and vegetables). Myitkyina, beside the Ayeyarwady river, is a cool, pleasant and beautiful place. Many people visit Myitkyina to see confluence of its two head streams (The Malikha and Maikha River), in addition, Eine Taw Gyi lake. Markets in Myitkyina are busy with visitors as a result.

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